

Notions On Semi μ_I -open set in GITS

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Abstract: In this article, we discuss some Kuratowski operators of Semi μ_I -open set and their characterizations are explain in detail. Also some notions of Semi μ_I -open set in GITS are to be defined and their relations between them are discussed.

Keywords: $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS, $S\mu_I$ -CSGITS, $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu I}$, $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu I}^c$, $i_{S\mu I}(A)$, $c_{S\mu I}(A)$

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1.Introduction: The conceptualization of intuitionistic set in topological space was first originate by Dogan Coker. In 2020, P.Sivagami, G.Helen Rajapushpam, G.Hari Siva Annam[11] discussed Generalized Intuitionistic Topological Space (GITS). In the past few years researchers twisted their raptness towards the different opensets and open functions which plays a vital role in mathematical science and engineering fields. Levine introduced semi open sets and semi continuity in general topology. Girija initiate the intuitionistic semi open set and characterize the properties of intuitionistic semi open set. Now in this article, we study about few operators in Semi μ_I -open set in GITS and their peculiarity reviewed.

2.Prelude:

On the whole paper, non-void set in GITS is termed as $\mathbb{X}$.

Definition:2.1[8]An intuitionistic set (IS) A is an object having the form $A = \langle \mathbb{X}, A_1, A_2 \rangle$, where $A_1, A_2 \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ satisfying $A_1 \cap A_2 = \phi$. The set A_1 is called the set of members of A while A_2 is called the set of non- members of A . Furthermore, let $\{A_i; i \in I\}$ be an arbitrary family of IS's in $\mathbb{X}$, where $A_i = \langle \mathbb{X}, A_i^{(1)}, A_i^{(2)} \rangle$ then

- 1) $\phi_{\sim} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \mathbb{X} \rangle$ and $X_{\sim} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \mathbb{X}, \phi \rangle$
- 2) $A \subseteq B$ if $A_1 \subseteq B_1$ and $A_2 \subseteq B_2$.

$$3) \bar{A} = \langle \mathbb{X}, A_2, A_1 \rangle.$$

$$4) A - B = A \cap \bar{B}.$$

$$5) \cap A_i = \langle \mathbb{X}, \cap A_i^{(1)}, \cup A_i^{(2)} \rangle \text{ and } \cup A_i = \langle \mathbb{X}, \cup A_i^{(1)}, \cap A_i^{(2)} \rangle.$$

Definition:2.2[2] Let $A \in \text{IS}(\mathbb{X})$ and $a \in \mathbb{X}$.

- (i) The form $\langle \{\mathbb{X}, \{a\}, \{a^c\}\rangle$ [resp. $\langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{a^c\}\rangle$] is called an intuitionistic point [resp. vanishing point] of $\mathbb{X}$ and denoted by a_I [resp. a_{IV}].
- (ii) We say that a_I [resp. a_{IV}] is contained in A , denoted by $a_I \in A$ [resp. $a_{IV} \in A$], if $a \in A_1$ [resp. $a \notin A_2$].

Definition:2.3[8] An intuitionistic topology on $\mathbb{X}$ is a family τ of intuitionistic sets in $\mathbb{X}$ containing $\phi_{\sim}, X_{\sim}$ and closed under finite union and arbitrary intersection. The pair $(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$ is called an intuitionistic topological space (ITS). Any intuitionistic set in τ is known as an intuitionistic open set (IOS) in $\mathbb{X}$ and the complement of IOS is called an intuitionistic closed set (ICS).

Definition:2.4[8] Let μ_I be the collection of intuitionistic subsets of $\mathbb{X}$. Then μ_I is called generalized intuitionistic topological space (GITS) on $\mathbb{X}$ if $\phi_{\sim} \in \mu_I$ and μ_I is closed under arbitrary unions. The elements of μ_I are called μ_I -open sets and their complements are called μ_I -closed sets. $c_{\mu_I}(A) = \cap \{F: F \text{ is } \mu_I\text{-closed set and } A \subseteq F\}$ and $i_{\mu_I}(A) = \cup \{G: G \text{ is } \mu_I\text{-open set, } G \subseteq A\}$.

Theorem:2.5[8] If $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -open (resp. μ_I -closed) iff $i_{\mu_I}(A) = A$ (resp. $c_{\mu_I}(A) = A$).

Results:2.6[8]

- 1) $A \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(A)$.
- 2) $c_{\mu_I}(A \cup B) \supseteq c_{\mu_I}(A) \cup c_{\mu_I}(B)$.
- 3) $c_{\mu_I}(A) \cap c_{\mu_I}(B) \supseteq c_{\mu_I}(A \cap B)$
- 4) $i_{\mu_I}(A \cup B) \supseteq i_{\mu_I}(A) \cup i_{\mu_I}(B)$.
- 5) $i_{\mu_I}(A \cap B) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}(A) \cap i_{\mu_I}(B)$.

Theorem:2.7[8]

- (a) $c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)}$,
- (b) $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$,
- (c) $\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$,

$$(d) c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})}.$$

Definition:2.8[5] An IS $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is said to be μ_I -nowhere dense if $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) = \mathfrak{C}$.

Theorem:2.9[5] If $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -nowhere dense then $i_{\mu_I}(A) = \mathfrak{C}$.

Throughout this paper, we call $\langle X, \phi, X \rangle$ as $\mathfrak{C}$, $\langle X, \phi, \phi \rangle$ as $\mathcal{O}$ and $\langle X, X, \phi \rangle$ as $\mathcal{U}$.

3. Semi μ_I -open set

Definition:3.1 An IS $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is said to be Semi μ_I -open set ($S\mu_I$ -OSGITS) if $A \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A))$.

The collection of Semi μ_I -open set is denoted by $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$.

Example:3.2 Let $\mathbb{X} = \{\mathfrak{K}_s, \mathfrak{L}_s, \mathfrak{M}_s\}$ and $\mu_I = \{\mathfrak{C}, \mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3\}$ where $\mathcal{S}_1 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{K}_s, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_2 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{M}_s, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_3 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{K}_s, \mathfrak{M}_s\}, \phi \rangle$. Then $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I} = \{\mathfrak{C}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_6\}$ where $\mathcal{S}_1 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{K}_s, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_2 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{M}_s, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_3 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{K}_s, \mathfrak{M}_s\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_4 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{K}_s, \mathfrak{M}_s\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_5 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{K}_s, \mathfrak{L}_s\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_6 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_s, \mathfrak{M}_s\}, \phi \rangle$.

Definition:3.3 The complement of $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS is called a Semi μ_I -closed set ($S\mu_I$ -CSGITS for short) (ie), $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) \subseteq A$. The collection of $S\mu_I$ -CSGITS is denoted by $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$.

Example:3.4 Let $\mathbb{X} = \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}, \mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}$ and $\mu_I = \{\mathfrak{C}, \mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_3, \mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_6, \mathcal{S}_7, \mathcal{S}_8\}$ where $\mathcal{S}_1 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}, \mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_2 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_3 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_4 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_5 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_6 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_7 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_8 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}\} \rangle$. Then $\mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c = \{\mathfrak{C}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{S}_1^c, \mathcal{S}_2^c, \mathcal{S}_3^c, \mathcal{S}_4^c, \mathcal{S}_5^c, \mathcal{S}_6^c, \mathcal{S}_7^c, \mathcal{S}_8^c, \mathcal{S}_9, \mathcal{S}_{10}, \mathcal{S}_{11}, \mathcal{S}_{12}\}$ where $\mathcal{S}_1^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_2^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_3^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_4^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_5^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_6^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_7^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_8^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}, \mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_9 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \phi \rangle, \mathcal{S}_{10} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_{11} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \{\mathfrak{L}_{sc}, \mathfrak{K}_{sc}\} \rangle, \mathcal{S}_{12} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathfrak{M}_{sc}\}, \{\mathfrak{K}_{sc}, \mathfrak{L}_{sc}\} \rangle$.

Theorem:3.5 Every μ_I -open is Semi μ_I -open but the reverse need not be true.

Proof: Suppose $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -open then $i_{\mu_I}(A) = A$. Now $c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A)) = c_{\mu_I}(A) \supseteq A \Rightarrow A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is Semi μ_I -open. The $\Leftarrow$ is not valid. In example 3.2, $\mathcal{S}_4, \mathcal{S}_5, \mathcal{S}_6$ are $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS but not a μ_I -open set.

Theorem:3.6 If $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$ then $A \cup B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$.

Proof: Suppose $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$, then $A \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A))$ & $B \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(B))$. Now $c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A \cup B)) \supseteq c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A) \cup i_{\mu_I}(B)) \supseteq c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(A)) \cup c_{\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(B)) \supseteq A \cup B \Rightarrow A \cup B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$.

Corollary:3.7 If $\{A_i\}_{i=1 \text{ to } \infty} \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$ then $\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$.

Remark:3.8 If $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$ then $A \cap B \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$. In example 3.2, $\mathcal{S}_2, \mathcal{S}_5 \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$ but $\mathcal{S}_2 \cap \mathcal{S}_5 = \emptyset \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}$.

Theorem:3.9 Every μ_I -closed is Semi μ_I -closed but the converse doesn't true.

Proof: Suppose $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -closed then $c_{\mu_I}(A) = A$. Now $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) = i_{\mu_I}(A) \subseteq A \Rightarrow A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is Semi μ_I -closed. The $\Leftarrow$ is not valid. In example 3.4, $\mathcal{S}_9, \mathcal{S}_{10}, \mathcal{S}_{11}, \mathcal{S}_{12}$ are $S\mu_I$ -CSGITS but not a μ_I -closed set.

Theorem:3.10 If $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$ then $A \cap B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$.

Proof: Suppose $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$, then $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) \subseteq A$ & $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(B)) \subseteq B$. Now $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A \cap B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A) \cap c_{\mu_I}(B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) \cap i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(B)) \subseteq A \cap B \Rightarrow A \cap B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$.

Remark:3.11 If $A, B \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$ then $A \cup B \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$. In example 3.2, $\mathcal{S}_4^c, \mathcal{S}_6^c \in \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$ but $\mathcal{S}_4^c \cup \mathcal{S}_6^c = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\mathcal{Q}_{SC}, \mathcal{K}_{SC}\}, \phi \rangle \notin \mathfrak{S}_{\mu_I}^c$.

Definition:3.12 Semi μ_I -interior and Semi μ_I -closure of $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is defined as follows:

$$i_{S\mu_I}(A) = \bigcup \{G : G \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, G \subseteq A\}$$

$$c_{S\mu_I}(A) = \bigcap \{F_S : F_S \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-CSGITS}, A \subseteq F_S\}$$

Note:3.13

- $i_{S\mu_I}(A)$ is the largest Semi μ_I -open set contained in A .
- $c_{S\mu_I}(A)$ is the smallest Semi μ_I -closed set containing A .

Result:3.14

$$\diamond i_{S\mu_I}(\mathfrak{C}) = \mathfrak{C}$$

$$\diamond c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{U}.$$

Remark:3.15

- $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{U}) \neq \mathcal{U}$ but $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{U})$ is the union of all $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS.
- $c_{S\mu_I}(\mathfrak{C}) \neq \mathfrak{C}$ but $c_{S\mu_I}(\mathfrak{C})$ is the intersection of all $S\mu_I$ -CSGITS.

Theorem:3.16 $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS (resp. $S\mu_I$ -CSGITS) iff $i_{S\mu_I}(A) = A$ (resp. $c_{S\mu_I}(A) = A$).

Proof: Obvious.

Theorem:3.17 For any $\mathcal{J}_1, \mathcal{J}_2 \subseteq \mathbb{X}$.

- If $\mathcal{J}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_2$ then $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2)$.
- $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2)$.

$$c) i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2).$$

Proof: a) Let $x_I \in i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1)$. Then $x_I \in \cup \{\mathbb{G}_S: \mathbb{G}_S \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, \mathbb{G}_S \subseteq \mathcal{J}_1\}$. Since $\mathcal{J}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_2$, $x_I \in \cup \{\mathbb{G}_S: \mathbb{G}_S \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, \mathbb{G}_S \subseteq \mathcal{J}_2\} \Rightarrow x_I \in i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2) \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2)$.

b) WKT $\mathcal{J}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2$ & $\mathcal{J}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2$. From a), $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2)$ & $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2)$. Therefore $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cup \mathcal{J}_2)$.

c) WKT $\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_1$ & $\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{J}_2$. From a), $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1)$ & $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2) \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1 \cap \mathcal{J}_2) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_2)$.

Remark:3.18 (a) The $\Leftarrow$ of a) is not true. For example, let $\mathbb{X} = \{\tilde{h}_s, \tilde{f}_s, \tilde{v}_s\}$ and $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, \mathcal{J}_1, \mathcal{J}_2, \mathcal{J}_3, \mathcal{J}_4, \mathcal{J}_5, \mathcal{J}_6, \mathcal{J}_7, \mathcal{J}_8, \mathcal{J}_9\}$ where $\mathcal{J}_1 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \phi, \tilde{f}_s \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_2 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s, \tilde{f}_s\}, \phi \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_3 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{f}_s\}, \{\tilde{h}_s, \tilde{v}_s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_4 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{f}_s\}, \phi \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_5 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s\}, \{\tilde{v}_s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_6 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s\}, \phi \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_7 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s, \tilde{f}_s\}, \{\tilde{v}_s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_8 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{f}_s\}, \{\tilde{h}_s\} \rangle$, $\mathcal{J}_9 = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s\}, \{\tilde{f}_s\} \rangle$. Here $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{O}) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9)$ but $\not\subseteq \mathcal{J}_9$.

(b) $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9 \cup \mathcal{O}) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_6) = \mathcal{J}_6$. Also $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{O}) = \mathcal{J}_9 \cup \mathcal{J}_1 = \mathcal{J}_9 \Rightarrow \mathcal{J}_9 \subset \mathcal{J}_6 \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{O}) \subset i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9 \cup \mathcal{O})$. $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_6^c \cup \mathcal{J}_1) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{O}) = \mathcal{J}_1$. Also $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_6^c) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) = \mathcal{J}_6^c \cup \mathcal{J}_1 = \mathcal{J}_1 \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_6^c) \cup i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_1) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_6^c \cup \mathcal{J}_1)$.

(c) $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_5 \cap \mathcal{J}_9) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_{10})$ [where $\mathcal{J}_{10} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{h}_s\}, \{\tilde{f}_s, \tilde{v}_s\} \rangle$] = $\mathcal{E}$. Also $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_5) = \mathcal{J}_9 \cap \mathcal{J}_5 = \mathcal{J}_6 \Rightarrow \mathcal{E} \subset \mathcal{J}_6 \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_5) \supset i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_9 \cap \mathcal{J}_5)$. $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_{11} \cap \mathcal{J}_8)$ [where $\mathcal{J}_{11} = \langle \mathbb{X}, \{\tilde{f}_s\}, \{\tilde{v}_s\} \rangle$] = $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_3) = \mathcal{J}_3$. Also $i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_{11}) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_8) = \mathcal{J}_3 \cap \mathcal{J}_8 = \mathcal{J}_3 \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_{11}) \cap i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_8) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{J}_{11} \cap \mathcal{J}_8)$.

Theorem:3.19 For any $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$,

$$a) i_{\mu_I}(A) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(A) \subseteq A.$$

$$b) i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(A)) = i_{S\mu_I}(A).$$

Proof: a) Suppose $x_I \in i_{\mu_I}(A)$, then $x_I \in \cup \{G: G \text{ is } \mu_I\text{-open set}, G \subseteq A\} \Rightarrow x_I \in \cup \{G: G \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, G \subseteq A\} \Rightarrow x_I \in i_{S\mu_I}(A)$. From the definition 3.6, $x_I \in A$. Henceforth $i_{\mu_I}(A) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(A) \subseteq A$.

b) From a), $i_{S\mu_I}(A) \subseteq A \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(A)) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(A)$. Let $B = i_{S\mu_I}(A)$ and let $x_I \in i_{\mu_I}(A) \Rightarrow x_I \in \cup \{G: G \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, G \subseteq A\} \Rightarrow x_I \in G$, for some $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS contained in $A \Rightarrow x_I \in G$, for some $S\mu_I$ -OSGITS contained in $B \Rightarrow x_I \in \cup \{G: G \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS}, G \subseteq B\} \Rightarrow x_I \in i_{\mu_I}(B) \Rightarrow x_I \in i_{\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(A)) \Rightarrow i_{S\mu_I}(A) \subseteq i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(A))$. Henceforth $i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(A)) = i_{S\mu_I}(A)$.

Theorem:3.20 For any $\mathcal{S}_1, \mathcal{S}_2, A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$.

- (i) If $\mathcal{S}_1 \subseteq \mathcal{S}_2$ then $c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_1) \subseteq c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (ii) $c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_1) \cup c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_2) \subseteq c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_1 \cup \mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (iii) $c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_1 \cap \mathcal{S}_2) \subseteq c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_1) \cap c_{S\mu_I}(\mathcal{S}_2)$.
- (iv) $A \subseteq c_{S\mu_I}(A) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(A)$.
- (v) $c_{S\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A)) = c_{S\mu_I}(A)$.

Theorem:3.21 For any $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$, we have

- (i) $c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A}) = \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)}$
- (ii) $\overline{c_{S\mu_I}(A)} = i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$
- (iii) $\overline{c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})} = i_{S\mu_I}(A)$
- (iii) $c_{S\mu_I}(A) = \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})}$.

Proof: i) Let $x_I \in c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$. Then $x_I \in \cap \{F_S: F_S \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-CSGITS}, \bar{A} \subseteq F_S\} \Rightarrow x_I \in F_S, \forall S\mu_I\text{-CSGITS } F_S$ such that $\bar{A} \subseteq F_S \Rightarrow x_I \notin \bar{F}_S$, for some $S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS } \bar{F}_S$ such that $\bar{F}_S \subseteq A \Rightarrow x_I \notin i_{S\mu_I}(A) \Rightarrow x_I \in \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)} \Rightarrow c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A}) \subseteq \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)}$. Suppose $x_I \notin c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$, then $x_I \notin \cap \{F_S: F_S \text{ is } S\mu_I\text{-CSGITS}, \bar{A} \subseteq F_S\} \Rightarrow x_I \notin F_S$, for some $S\mu_I\text{-CSGITS}$ contains $\bar{A} \Rightarrow x_I \in \bar{F}_S$ for some $S\mu_I\text{-OSGITS } \bar{F}_S$ such that $\bar{F}_S \subseteq A$ and consequently $x_I \in i_{S\mu_I}(A) \Rightarrow x_I \notin \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)} \Rightarrow \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)} \subseteq c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$ and then $c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A}) = \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)}$.

(ii),(iii) and (iv) follows from (i).

Theorem:3.22 If $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ then

- (i) $c_{S\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$.
- (ii) $i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$.

Proof: (i) $c_{S\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = c_{S\mu_I}(\overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)}) = \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(\iota_{S\mu_I}(A))} = \overline{\iota_{S\mu_I}(A)} = c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$.

(ii) $i_{S\mu_I}(i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = i_{S\mu_I}(\overline{c_{S\mu_I}(A)}) = \overline{c_{S\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A))} = \overline{c_{S\mu_I}(A)} = i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})$.

Theorem:3.23 If $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -nowhere dense then the following are true.

- (i) $i_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A)) = \emptyset$.
- (ii) $c_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = \mathcal{U}$.
- (iii) $i_{S\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A))) = \emptyset$.
- (iv) $c_{S\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A}))) = \mathcal{U}$

Proof: (i) Suppose $A \subseteq \mathbb{X}$ is μ_I -nowhere dense then $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) = \mathfrak{C}$. Now $i_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) = \mathfrak{C}$.

$$(ii) c_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A}) = \overline{i_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})} = \bar{\mathfrak{C}} = \dot{U}.$$

$$(iii) \text{From (i), } i_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A)) = \mathfrak{C}. i_{S\mu_I}(i_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(A))) = i_{S\mu_I}(\mathfrak{C}) = \mathfrak{C}.$$

$$(iv) \text{From (ii), } c_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A})) = \dot{U}. c_{S\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(c_{S\mu_I}(\bar{A}))) = c_{S\mu_I}(\dot{U}) = \dot{U}.$$

References:

- [1] J. Antony Rex Rodgio, Jessie Theodore and Hanaselvi Jansi.J, Notions via β^* - open sets in topological spaces, IOSR journal of mathematics e-ISSN:2278-5728, p-ISSN:2319-765X, vol 6.
- [2] Dogan Coker, A note on intuitionistic sets and intuitionistic points, Tr.J.of Mathematics 20 (1996) 343-351.
- [3] Dogan Coker, An introduction to intuitionistic topological spaces, BUSEFAL81(2000).
- [4] G.Helen Rajapushpam, P.Sivagami and G. Hari siva annam, Some new operators on $\mu_I g$ -closed sets in GITS, J.Math.Comput.Sci.11(2021),No:2,1868-1887, ISSN:1927-5307,.
- [5] G.Helen Rajapushpam, P.Sivagami and G. Harisivaannam, $\mu_I g$ -Dense sets and $\mu_I g$ -Baire Spaces in GITS, Asia Mathematica, Vol:5, Issue:1, (2021) Pages:158-167.
- [6] J.H.Kim, P.K.Lim, J.G.Lee, K.Hur, Intuitionistic topological spaces, Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Infomatics, 14 December 2017.
- [7] N.Raksha Ben, G.Hari siva annam, Generalized topological spaces via neutrosophic sets, J. Math.Comput.Sci. ISSN:1927-5307. SIS 2008.
- [8] P.Sivagami, G.Helen Rajapushpam, and G. Hari siva annam, intuitionistic Generalized closed sets in Generalized intuitionistic topological space, Malaya Journal Of Matematik, vol.8, No3, 1142-1147. E ISSN:2251-5666, P ISSN:2319-3786.